

Deliverable 6.2

Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

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ATU

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Executive Summary

This report is the first deliverable of Task 6.3 “Data Management³” and describes the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EmpowerUs project, funded by EU’s ‘EU Horizon Europe Programme’ on 1st October 2022 and will run for three years under the grant number 101059957.

The main objective of EmpowerUs DMP is to provide a comprehensive overview of all datasets gathered and generated as part of the project and to summarize the data management policy of the EmpowerUs consortium as it relates to these datasets.. The methodology to produce the EmpowerUs DMP is based on the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) guidelines and follows the structure of Horizon Europe DMP template.

The first version of the EmpowerUs DMP demonstrates the overall approach and policy for handling data management concerns on both an administrative and technological level. It reflects the status of the data that is collected, processed, or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. This initial version of the DMP defines the general policy and approach to data management in EmpowerUs that handles data management related issues on the administrative and technical level. This includes for example topics like data and meta-data collection, publication, and deposition of open data. The EmpowerUs DMP adhere to the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

The current version summarises the current data collection activities that are happening for the project. It also discusses about the FAIR guidelines and data repository for the data management. The DMP will evolve during the lifespan of the project. Next versions will refine and enhance policy aspects and will go into more detail regarding the datasets collected and produced by the EmpowerUs project partners.

Key words: Data Management Plan, EmpowerCoast, data accessibility, findability, interoperability

³ The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan (‘DMP’) is established and regularly updated. The use of this template is recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries. In completing the sections of the template the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17, must be addressed.

List of abbreviations

CA: Consortium Agreement

CO: Coordinator

DMP: Data Management Plan

DOI: Digital Object Identifier

FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets

ERC: European Research Council

GA: Grant Agreement

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GIS: Geographic Information System

KER: Key Exploitable Results

NBS: Nature Based Solution

OGC: Open Geospatial Consortium

OpenDOAR: Directory of Open Access Repositories

REA: European Research Executive Agency

Re3data: Registry of Research Data Repositories

SWOT: Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

TCL: Transition Coastal Lab

TEP: Tailored Empowerment Program

UKRI: UK Research and Innovation

WP: Work Package

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1.1. Background: About the EmpowerUs project

EmpowerUs is a three-year EU funded project aiming to support the coastal communities to work towards achieving the environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Coastal regions are highly vulnerable to climate change as they are affected by multiple parameters such as rainfall, flooding, temperature, wind, wave height, sea-level-rise and erosion. The communities along these coasts face many challenges such as extreme weather events, land-subsidence, salt-water intrusion, decrease in fisheries resources due to climate change. Europe has a very long coastline as a centre for important economic, environmental, and social activities and sites. Important ports, offshore energy production, and fishing are all concentrated along the coast, and with consequently in recent years, marine-coastal conflicts have been growing consistently. EmpowerUs is a multidisciplinary project that will support coastal communities as they transition to becoming more environmentally, economically, and socially sustainable by recognizing these complex challenges and implementing integrated solutions.

The EmpowerUs project aims to support resilient, inclusive, and sustainable coastal development activities and empower coastal communities to start acting now. The assessment measures will involve the gathering, processing, and storage of a wide range of data sets pertaining to wide range of coastal climate parameters and adaptation assessment. The project will inspire and enable coastal communities to tackle the most pressing environmental, economic and social challenges that exist in their communities.

Figure 1: EmpowerUs, WPs link

Through a network of six Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) spread throughout Europe, EmpowerUs will create an adaptable transformation mechanism. Through TCLs, they will construct a network of communities and share knowledge to collectively develop new knowledge with multi-actors that can address the different challenges that coastal communities confront. The TCLs will have access to the

challenges and co-creation framework to address challenges relevant to their region. Through seven working packages, the EmpowerUs will assist coastal communities to address crucial environmental, economic, and social concerns that are present in their respective communities.

The flux of data through research WPs is sketched in the diagram shown in Figure 1, whereas the following text will detail which data are used by WPs. EmpowerUs will co-create co-pilot and co-evaluate tailored empowerment programmes by collaborating with multiple stakeholders from local, regional, national and international level. To support social innovations that increase socio-economic resilience, wellbeing, and employment opportunities for diverse communities, EmpowerUs will incorporate a portfolio of flexible, transdisciplinary tools, ensuring that no one is left behind. Additionally, practical guidance on implementing nature-based solutions to address environmental problems by EmpowerUs will enable communities to take ownership of their climate resilience.

The Programmes will be implemented across a network of six pilot sites located in Bulgaria (Burgas Province), Cyprus (Eastern Limassol Region), Finland (Åland Islands), Ireland (West Coast), Norway (North), and Spain (Northwestern Mediterranean).

1.2. Rationale

The EmpowerUs Data Management Plan (DMP) will collect data, develop algorithms and models to automatize data collection, enrichment and analysis. The goal of the program is to foster access to data generated from the EmpowerUS project, so that the data becomes accessible, re-usable and benefit the various stakeholders. For the data gathering and storage, the consortium will ensure the secure environment, and that it will comply to the ethical and legal standards such as consent and/or anonymity of the data provider/owner for the use of data. The DMP will ensure that the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679), which governs the management of data records including personal information, is followed.

1.3. Objectives

The EmpowerUs DMP will be accomplished through different dissemination and exploitation actions, to outline the policies and procedures to be followed by the consortium by ensuring that the data gathered and collected is managed correctly. These actions further aim at communicating project results to key stakeholders by engaging with the task leaders to organise workshops, educational activities and the publication of articles concerning projects results, to ensure open access policy for Horizon Europe project guidelines.

The DMP will ensure effective external communication and dissemination of the EmpowerUs project results, including stakeholder engagement, to support uptake of knowledge results at different levels and maximise impact and legacy. It should serve as a manual for all data management procedures to be followed in the EmpowerUs project while also providing background information and rationale for each procedure in the context of Horizon Europe.

The DMP package:

1. Covers the data management life cycle for the EmpowerUs project data collection, processing and/or generation.

2. Will analyse the key components of the DMP that the consortium shall employ to manage all of the EmpowerUS data, documentation and metadata
3. Will ensure that the research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR)
4. Create a List of data collected and generated, then preserve the data for long-term archival in accordance with the data policy requirements
5. Will ensure the ethical and legal compliance of the project.

1.4. The DMP approach

EmpowerUs will follow the EU horizon guidelines for open innovation. Open science is the key to allow knowledge to spread more quickly and make it easily accessible. Through the scientific publications and research data availability, the adaptations will progress more rapidly for the existing challenges. The approach is to follow the EU 's Open Science Policy to acquire and generate data from multiple sources, saving and accessibility of that data. It is also expected that after the completion of the project, DMP will continue to do so after the project has ended using various available platforms. A crucial component of the project in this context is the DMP, that details how the data has been gathered or generated within the project and how it will be organized, stored, and shared. Furthermore, the DMP will detail which data will be made available to the public through open repositories and which, to the extent practicable, will only be made available to the consortium (confidential), beginning with the project's inception. Regarding data and information sensitivity, current law and policies will be taken into consideration for various countries involved in the project.

All grants must manage the research data produced in projects supported by Horizon Europe. Each beneficiary is responsible for ensuring that the research data generated in the project is carefully managed in accordance with the FAIR principles ([AGA Article 17 – Annex 5](#)).

Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Partners are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the EmpowerUs project (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem.

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The data gathered and produced will have a metadata, however the form/format of the metadata has yet to be established. With the data gathered, a visual story map for blue justice stories will be created online and will be partially accessible to the public. As the project progresses, the accessibility also changes. Nevertheless, after the project completion, the publicly available data will remain online for

five years. As part of the DMP, all EC reporting stages will be reviewed with regards to how the project responds to the FAIR principles.

1.5. DMP revision plan for EmpowerUs

EmpowerUs will acquire and generate data from multiple sources, and it is expected that it will continue to do so after the project has ended.

While the first version of the DMP primarily focuses on data collected, the second version will include report on data produced in the framework of the project as well as non-sensitive data that can be made publicly accessible in open data repositories and registered at relevant catalogues. The accessibility, and privacy policy will be explained in much broader way in the next version of the DMP.

The final DMP report, which will include comprehensive information about the project's data collection and the data generated for all tasks, will be developed at the project's conclusion.

2. Data Summary

The project will require the collection, processing and storage of various datasets from all the EmpowerUs partners. As the data identification and collection activities are still ongoing, the first version of the DMP primarily focuses on data collection techniques/approaches, while little details were provided for data format and the potential memory needed. The second version will include report on data produced in the framework of the project as well as non-sensitive data that can be made publicly accessible in open data repositories and registered at relevant catalogues. The final version of the DMP will be prepared by the project end and will give full details about the project data collection and data produced for all the tasks. A detailed descriptions of the datasets, accessibility and other questionnaire that are relevant to all the WPs for preparing the current DMP version are available in Annex 1.

An initial survey has been carried out from the EmpowerUs partners to gather the data information, each work-package (WP) and their data summary has been provided in the following sub-sections:

2.1. WP1: Project management and coordination

The data gathered in this work package will be in document format. The primary objective is to audit the entire project; however, there are no specific deliverables that may be provided in terms of data gathering or data production from this package.

2.2. WP2: Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)

From WP2, **TCLs is one of the focal points for the EmpowerUs activities** as it will will coordinate the design, implementation and evaluation activities.

The data will be stored in text format and potentially SPSS.. The expected size of individual datasets ranges between a few MB and 1 GB. However, raw datasets can include large numbers of files gathered for the study and inclusion of local community knowledge. The data will preferentially be processed offline by individual experts, while the aggregated data, data necessary for functionality will be stored on designated project specific or institutional data (cloud) data store, such as SharePoint. Apart from local data that is subject to complex agreements, the data stored in these joint or institutional data stores will have full access policy for the project partners and will be considered for open access publication in open access repositories unless restricted by third-party copyrights or confidentiality agreements. Description of local data, including accessibility and licensing aspects to

allow data to be re-usable within EmpowerUs and to produce datasets to be publicly available, will be provided in the next releases of the EmpowerUs DMP.

2.3. WP3: Participatory methods to support social transition and innovation

This work package will build upon previous package, specifically on Task 2.1, which will assess local resources, previous decision-making processes and the stakeholder typology for each planning area. Currently, the Eklipse process has been extensively utilized to discuss the relationship between nature-based solutions (NBS), ecosystem services, coastal issues and a document (pdf) has been prepared. The next stage will establish a baseline for WP2 by identifying the barriers, drivers of change, and megatrends necessitated for social transition in coastal communities and the Blue Economy. The package will gather data through SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats), questionnaires and interviews. The data will be in the doc and pdf formats, and the anticipated size has not yet been established. Through the EmpowerUs SharePoint workspace, all partners have access to the data, however, part of the data will have limited access for the stakeholders from outside the EmpowerUs project. This is to protect individuals and organizations. as per the Norwegian Centre for Research Data regulations.

2.4. WP4: Evidence-based, nature-based solutions for cross sectoral innovation

The main objective of this work package is to improve the ecological resilience by supporting the six TCLs in finding a range of nature-based solutions and social innovations. The tools to gather data for this package are with problem tree, interviews, focus group, SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats), mental mapping, force field analysis, observation, questionnaire and any other means available to get the information such as co-creation tools. The data format is in doc, excel and/or pdf format with expected memory size from a few MB to a few GB approximately. For the accessibility, the stakeholders will get their own folder with data (sensitive data are not openly accessible). Raw data from questionnaire surveys and interviews will be anonymized and partly restricted (and thus will be available for internal use only/within the project consortium). However, data will be published in the journals as open access and thus publicly available.

2.5. WP5: Synthesis of Inclusive Transition Mechanisms that enable just, sustainable outcomes.

The primary goal for this work package is to synthesise lessons and inputs from WP2, WP3 and WP4 by examining and identifying what social and cultural practices, economic activities and governance arrangements that are resilient under rapid change and uncertainty. By synthesising the challenges, barriers and preconditions across all TCLs, WP5 will produce a roadmap on the design of transition mechanisms and a handbook on inclusive methodologies that focus on equity. The results will be made available to the public as the project moves forward. To safeguard people and organizations, some of the qualitative data will be restricted, but the remaining data can still be obtained with the necessary authorization. As the type and extent of these datasets depend on work in progress, more details will be provided in the next version of the DMP.

2.6. WP6: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Ocean Literacy

WP6 will implement the PDEC with the involvement of all partners and outline concrete and targeted measures related to communication, dissemination, knowledge management, and exploitation activities for EmpowerUs and deliver tailored knowledge transfer plans for Key Exploitable Results

(KERs). It will further involve the TEPs conducted by TCLs in (WP2) and ensure to reach end-users with the support of WP leaders and the Innovation partners. As per the requirement of EC, access policy to scientific publications will be implemented. All the publication, in addition to the publisher's archive, will be also stored in an online repository, where it can be easily linked to deposited datasets and at partners' institutional repositories.

For project internal administrative needs as well as external dissemination, community development, and exploitation operations, WP6 data is primarily engaged in user account and profile information. This includes both personal data of EmpowerUs partners staff used to manage the project's mailing lists and document repository and personal data of outside users used to provide functionality to the EmpowerUs community (newsletters, event invitations, etc.). The datasets include details like names, organizations, email addresses, roles, etc. that are mostly gathered directly from the users when they register on the relevant websites and confirmed.

The first version of the DMP is submitted in M6 of the project in a document format, that is end of March 2023. As the project progresses, the data will be made available in EmpowerUs website in the forms of images, videos, and documents. There will be revisions to the DMP and will be made during the project as visibility increases around the nature, volume, formats, etc. of the data. At minimum, the DMP should be reviewed and updated, if necessary, before review meetings, and once in M18 and the other at the end of the project (M36).

2.7. WP7 – Ethics requirements

The consortium of this project places a high priority on data protection and ethical research practices. When conducting research, good ethics follow all procedures to guard against the misuse of sensitive data. For this project, the consortium seeks to guarantee this. WP7 ensures that the partners must comply with the ethics and research integrity (see GA Article 34 from Horizon Europe grants manual webpage mentioned in the annex 3 links). The data collected will be kept in document form for the benefit of the stakeholders, and it will adhere strictly to the EU project ethics guidelines. Further, the document outlines will be regularly updated in the EmpowerUs website.

3. FAIR data

This document considers the latest “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe”. The EmpowerUs project partners should make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) and ensure that is soundly managed, allowing for maximum knowledge circulation. This DMP describes the data management procedures that are followed according to the FAIR principles and the Horizon Europe guidelines for their implementation. To prepare the DMP FAIR data, we used annex 1 of the Horizon Europe grants manual data management template. The template is a set of questions that one should answer with a level of detail appropriate to the project, however the detail of the project is ongoing and will be revised in the next versions of the DMP.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1. Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find through online search. To ensure the automatic discoverability of datasets and services, machine-readable metadata are essential. For the publication of project results, all project partners will deposit and describe the

relative underlying dataset(s), keywords and unique identifiers to make them findable. Further, the data can be accessible through their Institutional repositories with a unique persistent identifier, such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

All partners are strongly recommended to make use of DOI to make datasets produced by EmpowerUs citable for publication. As the chosen repositories need to support standard descriptive metadata to ensure datasets indexing and discoverability also by machines, we recommend all the partners to use a repository such as Zenodo, which is one of the open data repositories that generates DOIs for research results. There are other such repositories recommended by European Research Council (ERC), such as Dryad, open science framework etc. Whether scientific publications will be assigned a unique identifier like DOI, Publisher Item Identifier (PII), International Standard Serial Number (ISSN), etc. depends on the open access strategy (green or gold) chosen by the editors and thus also on the respective scientific publisher and the chosen research repository. Further details about DOI will be discussed in 3.1.4.

3.1.2. What naming conventions do you follow?

File names will include version numbers, and time-frame in terms of month. Typically, the name convention will follow with WP (Work package number), or the task number (e.g. T2.1) or deliverable (e.g. D2.2).

The naming convention for each work package is described as follows:

“WPNumber_TaskNumber_PartnerName_DatasetName_Version_DateOfStorage”.

3.1.3. Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Identifiers: All open EmpowerUs results deposited in a repository will provide search keywords together with their metadata, further clarity is provided in 3.1.5. Keywords for open data will be selected from controlled vocabularies that are suitable for the specific type of the data (see 3.3.3).

3.1.4. Do you provide clear version numbers?

The version numbers will be provided as discussed in section 3.1.3. Additionally, all open data, publications and open-source software will be deposited in a repository, such as Zenodo repository and will use DOI versioning. DOI versioning allows for updating a dataset after it has been published and to cite either a specific version of a dataset or all versions of a dataset.

3.1.4. What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The EU horizon template clearly mentioned the necessity for the rich **metadata** that significantly improves the findability and re-usability of any project’s data.

For EmpowerUs will adopt to Dublin core standards of metadata, with the following deposition metadata fields:

- **Creators:** The creators/authors of the deposition
- **Contributor:** The contributor, responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
- **Publisher:** An entity responsible for making the resource available
- **Title:** Title of the deposition.
- **Date:** Date of publication in ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD).

- **Language:** language of the data content of the resource.
- **Format:** Typically, Format may include the media-type or dimensions of the resource. Format may be used to identify the software, hardware, or other equipment needed to display or operate the resource. Examples of dimensions include size and duration (reference: Dublin core).
- **Subject:** A topic of the content of the resource.
- **Description:** An account of the content of the resource.
- **Identifier:** Identify the resource by means of a string or number, such as DOI
- **Relation:** A reference to a related resource by means of a string or number
- **Source:** Reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived
- **Type:** Type includes terms describing general categories, functions, genres, or aggregation levels for content
- **Coverage:** Coverage will include spatial location (a place name or geographic coordinates), temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administrative entity).
- **Rights:** Typically, Rights will contain a rights management statement for the resource, or reference a service providing such information.

Further, if a GIS based platform is developed, the EmpowerUs DMP will

- Use a GIS framework based on the requirements of the INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC
- Comply with standards and specifications relevant to spatial data, such as the ones set by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) aiming to make location information FAIR.
- Apply the OGC standards for the interoperability of data.
- Ensure that metadata linked to the datasets enable standardized organization and discovery of geospatial data, in line with the INSPIRE directive: ISO 19115-1:2014 Geographic information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals, ISO 19139:2007 Geographic information - Metadata - XML Implementation

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find through online search. To ensure the automatic discoverability of datasets and services, machine-readable metadata are essential. EmpowerUs has its own publicly available website, that gives complete details about the package, its progress and the partners associated. The partners will be asked to select the most appropriate data repositories that facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are the basic principles for the Horizon Europe project to comply with. Although during the project life, data will be managed through the common Sharepoint and regularly updating EmpowerUs webpage, for the publication of project results, each research teams will deposit and describe the relative underlying dataset(s), keywords and unique identifiers to find them. Further, the data can be accessible through their Institutional **repositories** with a unique persistent identifier, such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

Partners are encouraged to consider the Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) and Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) for helpful listings of repositories that may be appropriate.

3.2. Making data Accessible:

3.2.1. Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

(Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement (CA) and are in line with the reasons for opting out.)

The EmpowerUs seeks to make data openly available, whenever possible, to allow for dissemination and validation, and to increase the re-use potential of research results. To achieve this, the datasets that will be deposited will have all relevant documentation and explanation, and all files will be converted to standard, well-documented open formats.

EmpowerUs will make sure to make the data access as open as possible, however there will be data required to be closed to maintain privacy/confidentiality. Such data access constraints or inability to share the data will only be taken into consideration in the following circumstances:

- When collected data is from third party and it denies the accessibility through EmpowerUs for confidentiality issues.
 - Protection of personal information or the stakeholder who provided the data for sensitivity and safety.
 - Legal issues relating to data used.
 - Any other legitimate reasons.
- To allow data sharing as much as possible, legitimate actions will be adopted such as:
- When collected data, copyrights will be obtained from third party owners, wherever is applicable.
 - Acknowledge the re-used data for external users and also for internal purposes. is from third party and it denies the accessibility through EmpowerUs for confidentiality issues, by providing all relevant documentation and explanation for the data and the datasets, including the procedures adopted to obtain them, versioning, and software for reading data in case of non-standardize formats.
 - Obtain the consent from citizens and stakeholders carried out by WP3 and WP4 surveys and interviews
 - in case of copyright on raw data derived, collected or elaborated from pre-existing databases or from other original sources (i.e., papers, journal articles, book chapters, reports, video and audio sources), collected data will be made available if the reproduction and sharing are allowed by expressed permission of the right holders or by applicable copyright exceptions and exemptions.

Wherever necessary, the EmpowerUs DMP indicates the versions or parts of the datasets that cannot be freely shared providing the specific motivations.

3.2.2. How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

EmpowerUs will have results repository that will be openly accessible in accordance with Horizon Europe guideline policy for 'open access to research data'.

EmpowerUs will have a results repository that will be openly available in accordance with Horizon Europe's requirements for open access to research data.

Open data: All open results will be accessible openly through an appropriate open access repository. Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (primarily published in academic journals), research data are other ways of providing accessibility.

For disseminating open access papers, including academic social network sites such as ResearchGate or Academia etc, are possible, for which, an electronic copy of the publication has to be deposited in suitable open access repository. However, the Horizon Europe project guidelines also encourage to use other online repositories that are mentioned in the above sections. To automate the process of reporting scientific publications and other research data, there are different ways such as green open access and gold open access that can be used depending upon the time frame under which the data needs to be disseminated. the EmpowerUS partners are encouraged to use such actions as per their needs.

- 3.2.3. What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?**
- 3.2.4. Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?**
- 3.2.5. Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- 3.2.6. Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?**
Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.
- 3.2.7. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?**
- 3.2.8. If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?**
- 3.2.9. Is there a need for a data access committee?**
- 3.2.10. Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?**
- 3.2.11. How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**

The EmpowerUs partners may not use any code to access the data, the basic software tools usable are listed in Table 1. All the remaining questions are to be answered in the revisions of the DMP as the EmpowerUs partners did not establish the kind of software, documentation, accessibility to their repositories, machine reliable licences as of now for the first version of DMP. In case agreements with third parties will restrict the access to specific users, the access will be managed through the permission system allowed by the cloud service and the identity of the accessing person will be ascertained before data provision.

Table 1: Software/tools used for DMP data accessibility

Tools/Software
open spreadsheet and document editors, such as <i>OpenOffice</i> or <i>LibreOffice</i>
free CSV file viewers, such as <i>CSV viewer</i>
open or free image viewers
VLC for mp3 and mpg

3.3. Making data interoperable

3.3.1. Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

This can only be partially answered, as the data collection is still in progress. However, most datasets are interviews, questionnaire, focus groups and knowledge sharing. If not applicable, datasets will be described using other metadata standard or metadata based on general purpose descriptive metadata, such as Dublin Core metadata Schema to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability or will follow the convention of the hosting research data repository. All relevant documentation explaining data collection procedures, analysis, and data quality information will be made available along with the data. This will guarantee the intelligibility, reproducibility and the validation of the project findings-

3.3.2. What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Vocabularies for keywords and other metadata properties have yet to be established, and next version may provide further insight.

Second sub-heading 3.3.3. Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

Vocabularies for keywords and other metadata properties have yet to be selected.

3.3.4. In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

For EmpowerUs, specific ontologies will be used, a mapping exercise to other ontologies will be undertaken.

3.4. Making data Re-Usable

3.4.1. How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

A Creative Commons license, ideally Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY-4.0) is advised for owners of open results produced from the EmpowerUs project notwithstanding the restrictions. The authors can preserve the ownership of their work through scientific publications, and open access repositories can allow accessibility to a wide range of stakeholders as well as to the public.

In order to preserve ownership of their work's copyright and deposit the publication in an Open Access repository, authors of scientific papers resulting from the EmpowerUs project are advised to negotiate a deal with the article's scientific publisher (see 2.2.3).

3.4.2. When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The research data required to verify the findings of the scientific articles will be given open access simultaneously with the publication.

3.4.3. Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

After the project is completed, third parties can still use any open results that were produced by the project and stored in the appropriate repository. If open access to specific research data required to verify a scientific publication is prohibited by confidentiality, security, privacy obligations, the data may be deposited in a restricted repository and access may be granted upon request and under the terms of a restricted license (See section 3.2 for restrictions).

3.4.4. How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The open results that are deposited in a repository will be available up to 5 years after the completion the project.

3.4.5. Are data quality assurance processes described?

The data quality assurance and process will be described by the ethics section. This will progress, from the first results published/produced for the EmpowerUs project.

4. Other research outputs

4.1. Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

As per our first survey currently, the project does not make use of procedures for data management other than those described in this data management policy.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1. What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Building on existing open science resources and Horizon Europe guidelines, it will document the policies and procedures to be followed by the EmpowerUs consortium for managing all data generated and collected during and after the project, including scientific outputs, new methodologies, protocols, processes, new approaches, modelling and digital database (EmpowerCoast). Any costs utilised for making the data FAIR in the future will be described in this part during project progress.

5.2. How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The costs will be covered through the Horizon Europe grant which is in compliance with the grant agreement. Currently, the exact details about the covering the amount has not been confirmed or decided. EmpowerUs has allocated a part of overall WP6 budget for these activities. For the open access research data, the HORIZON EUROPE grant guidelines will be strictly followed.

At present, the EmpowerUs project grant includes, €24,000 for the cloud-based knowledge sharing platforms, €20,000 for the WP2 data management system, €2,000 for the conferences, and €3,000 for open access publications.

5.3. Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management activities concern the whole project and needs to be coordinated and monitored both at project and work package level. Data management is also linked to publication of project results and thus dissemination activities. The primary responsibility is held by ERINN Innovation, while all the project partners will contribute through the activity updates. DMP versions will be prepared by ATU through surveys.

5.4. Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

The long-term preservation of data as per the Horizon Europe guidelines will be available up to 5 years after the completion the project in the data repository. The Zenodo repository may be encouraged to use as of now (See section 5.1). The EmpowerUS consortium will decide, how and how long the data will be retained. The next version of DMP will cover the cost details for the allocation of resources.

6. Data security

6.1 What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

During the duration of the project, relevant research data will be managed through sharepoint. At each partner, research data will be stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives accessible through institutional passwords periodically modified according to national law provisions for data

security and protected by regularly updated antiviruses. None of the project data will be left inadvertently available. All the research materials stored in computers are subject to regular backup to safeguard them from accidental losses. The data results will be encouraged to put in Zenodo as well for long term preservation.

6.2 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and curation?

The selected data repositories, which have specified preservation standards, enable long-term preservation of public data. For instance, Zenodo policy guarantees that the items will be kept for the duration of the repository, and best efforts will be made to integrate all information into appropriate substitute institutional and/or subject-based repositories in the event of closure.

7. Ethical aspects

7.1. Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

All currently identified ethical parameters to be obeyed will be documented in WP7 - “Ethics requirements”. Before making the data accessible, all relevant open access datasets will also address ethical issues. The EmpowerUs project will not produce research results which are sensitive to personal and ethical concerns. The EmpowerUs project has assigned an ‘ethics and security board’, which will monitor and make decisions related to the ethics and security. Additional details will be reported, as needed, in future versions of the DMP.

7.2. Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Each WP deliverable will follow strict guidelines of ethics with proper assistance by WP7. The ethical standards for public accessibility of sensitive data will be maintained, and anonymity of personal information of data provider will as well. WP7 also informs EmpowerUs project partners when and where approvals are needed and how to deal with personal data. Further on, it is communicated where informed consent is needed and how to get them, e.g., addressing informed consent procedure for communication with stakeholders. Additional details will be provided in WP7 “Ethics requirements” deliverables which are currently work in progress.

8. Conclusion

The EmpowerUs DMP is based upon the datasets for procedures and infrastructure that are anticipated at this point in the project. The next deliverable is scheduled for M18 (March 2024). A draft of the updated DMP may be provided before M18 in order to facilitate in the official project review process. The next step of actions will be on the semantics, further methodology elaboration, participant and stakeholder involvement, and the identification of areas that require special attention. The next DMP releases will provide an overview of the datasets produced or being produced, by EmpowerUs through a table that will be filled and updated in (Table 2).

Each entry in the table corresponds to a dataset that will be described with specific information such as those requested in ARGO templates. ARGOS is an open source, configurable and extensible tool for planning Research Data Management (RDM) activities according to Open Access & FAIR data policies. Argos tool has been integrated with Zenodo services, to help implement and accelerate open science. A sample table, with guidance, developed following ARGOS templates is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: list of datasets of EmpowerUs project (acronyms and abbreviations: # = dataset progressive number ID, Project phase (starting month-ending month), "Creator team" is the team in charge of curating the dataset; C=collected/ G=generated; A=available, P=in pro

#	WP	Lead Beneficiary	TASK	Project PhaseP	CT	DATASET Title	SOURCE	STATUS
1	1	NRI	X.Y	1-6	ERINN	EmpowerUs: WPX:.....: TaskX.1: T-----	C, A	ZZZ

Annex 1: Daya Survey template for version 1

The EmpowerUs data Survey Template is used to collect information on used and produced datasets according to the requirements of the EmpowerUs Data Management Plan with help of EmpowerUs's technical coordination site (<https://EmpowerUs-project.eu/>).

1. Location
2. Email address
3. What overall challenge(s) will you try to solve under the framework of the EmpowerUs project? Please describe the challenge as a short problem statement and describe your data type.
4. What tools will you use (are using) to collect the data (You can select multiple)
5. If "Others" in the survey, mention the tool
6. What is the timeline for your task updates (Please refer to the time period in months for example: M6, M18)? What is the expected format and the size (memory) of the data delivered? (Example: doc...)
7. What is the origin of the data that you are using for the EmpowerUs project? The data can be primary or secondary, if it is secondary, please provide the source details.
8. To whom will your gathered/generated data be useful for?
9. Does your task in EmpowerUs utilise GIS software?
10. If yes, what techniques are they expecting to use? (If not mention NA)
11. What stakeholders do you plan to involve in your working objectives?
12. Please specify the type and the name of the organizations
13. For the already identified stakeholders, what are their main needs, motivations, and expectations?
14. How will the roles and responsibilities be shared among stakeholders?
15. For end-users, are there specific required skills and competencies required for reusing the data?
16. If yes, please specify the required skills and competencies
17. What level of involvement is expected from end-users?
18. What is the discoverability of the data your work package generates (i.e. the metadata)? 19. What form or format will the metadata describing your data take?
20. Will your data be openly available? If any part of data is restricted, please provide a justification explaining why here? If your data is (partly-) restricted, is there any access code to get the...
21. Does your output need any specific tools or software to access it?
22. Do you intend to make use of digital visualisation systems for your generated data? Can your data be integrated into a digital system?
23. If Yes, which part of your data can be used for replication and re-used for understanding different scenarios. (If no mention NA)
24. Can a third-party use/re-use your generated data ?
25. If yes for the above survey, can it be re-used even after the end of the project? (Specify the length of time that data can be re-used).
26. If No for the above survey, Explain Why (need to give rationale, as per FAIR guidelines)
27. Does your data require a license to be re-used and re-distributed widely? (As per FAIR policy, data is encouraged to be available to wider communities/stakeholders)
28. Does your data have back-up/ data-recovery facility?
29. Is your data safely stored in any certified storage repositories for long-term preservation and curation?
30. Does your data have any ethical or legal considerations that can have an impact on data sharing?

31. Do project stakeholders/partners involved in the EmpowerUs project have access to the processes and results, or do they require permission from you to re-use them?
32. If "Other" (elaborate, example: permission needed from the owner or simply an acknowledgment/reference needed to re-use the data))
33. Are these same processes/outcomes available to public?
34. If "No" for the above survey, what part of the outcome will be accessible to the public?
35. Does the project partners and stakeholders involved in decision making process planning to build a policy and programe document library?
36. If "Yes" for the above survey question, Does the policy documentary cover any of the following ?
37. Which style of documentary (activities) can be expected from your task?

Annex 2: Sample data description form to be used for next DMP version

#	Status: Available	EmpowerUs: WPX:: Task X.1: (short title of the dataset)		
ID [ID type]		Provide DOI or url		
Filename(s)		Specify name(s) according to filename rules written in section 3.1		
Team in charge		Partner(s) name(s), orcid(s)		
Description		This dataset contains data on [...] The dataset is organized as follows [...]		
Purpose of the data collection/generation in relation to the project/WP/Task objectives		Add appropriate description		
To whom might data be useful?		Add appropriate description		
Accessibility		Please provide Lincensing information (see section 3.1)		
Creator/s		"Creator" is the team in charge of curating the dataset		
Contributor/s		"Contributors" are people contributing in different way to create the dataset		
Contact Person/s		(name, organization, email, and ORCID of contact person)		
Related publications		Specify Project deliverable(s) OA publication(s) related to the dataset		
Type of data		Primary/Secondary	Collected/Generated	Qualitative/Quantitative
Data format		Describe the data format; if in the format is not in Table 1 , please describe it and provide a link a software to read such format.		
Data reused for generating the dataset		Leave empty for primary data or specify the dataset(s) providing identifier or url or other sources and evidence of right to reuse (licensing)		
Data Volume		Final volume of data is/ is expected to be [XXX] (in the appropriate unit).		
How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?		Data will be/are made available in YYY repository under under a (CC BY 4.0) or (ODC-By) license. or: Data will not be available for reuse because of [...please specify ...] or: Data are of limited use kept on secure, managed storage for the limited time of [specify] years or: Accessible via SIP		
Legal issues that can have an impact on sharing this dataset		Not applicable or : Explain legal issues eventually referring to D11.1 if related to use of personal data		
What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?		If applicable, describe the specific method used for processing sensitive/personal data		
Will you use metadata to describe the data ?		If yes, please specify them and if they (and at what extent): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use standardized vocabularies • be available free of charge • be harvestable ? 		
Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?		Provide DOI or not, in case data are not finalized for repositories		
Are services used to provide searchable metadata?		SIP, Registry/Catalogue, OpenAIR		
Will/Do your metadata describe the quality of the data?		Recommended for sensors data		
Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?		See WP7		

Will your data be openly accessible?	Please specify
How will the data be made available?	e.g. GIS based platform, project website, repositories, etc ...
Will/do you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?	Please specify
Do you the team have documented procedures for quality assurance of data?	These should be included also in metadata
Will/Do the team provide any support for data reuse?	Through readme and descriptive files and/or offering curator(s) contacts
How long the team will support data reuse?	Up to [please specify] years

Annex 3: Links for online open access information for DMP

<https://enspire.science/data-management-plan-in-horizon-europe/>
<https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>
<https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/technical-solutions-and-tools/persistent-identifiers>
<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
<http://help.zenodo.org/features/>
<https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-rdm>
[https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document open Research Data and Data Management Plans.pdf](https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document_open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf)
<https://datadryad.org/>
<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
www.re3data.org
<https://osf.io/>
<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/2003-06-02/>
<https://www.w3.org/TR/NOTE-datetime>
www.Openoffice.com
<https://csvviewer.com/>
<https://www.xnview.com>
<https://www.videolan.org>
<http://opendefinition.org/licenses/cc-by/>
<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>

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